

MODELLING MACHINE INTELLIGENCE MEASURING

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ABSTRACT

Although the number and diversity of intelligent agent-based systems (IABSs), also known as agentic systems, evolve very rapidly, the main difficulty of measuring the intelligence of intelligent systems, also referred to as machine intelligence, remains. Previously, we have developed some novel intelligence metrics for measuring machine intelligence, namely *MetrIntPairII*, *ExtrIntDetect*, and *MetrIntSimil*. In this paper, the focus is on the *MetrIntSimil* metric. *MetrIntSimil* can measure the intelligence of an arbitrary set of IABSs, calculating their so-called intelligence quotients that are comparable, the IABSs with the same intelligence are classified in the same classes. *MetrIntSimil* is based on complex data science and statistical analysis. A difficult-to-decide use case is presented in that it studies and compares the intelligence of a set of intelligent systems using *MetrIntSimil*. Difficulties in the analysis consist of aspects like different well-known normality tests giving contradictory results, decision on outlier removal, decision between parametric and non-parametric statistical tests, and others. This is also illustrative to the artificial intelligence research, when the experimental results must be analysed using advanced data science and statistical methods.

INTRODUCTION

Intelligent agent-based systems (IABSs) include intelligent agents (IAs), who solves individually problems (Iantovics 2006) and intelligent cooperative multiagent systems (CMSs), where the member agents cooperate in problem-solving (Iantovics and Enăchescu 2009).

IABSs development is a challenging, evolving field. Wen et al. (2025) proposed an IA for the problem of acupuncture-based infertility treatment decisions. Ghasemi (2025) proposed a CMS for solving the multi-robot flight formation problem. Xu et al. (2025) proposed an intelligent agent-based system for geotechnical design. Kandiri et al. (2025) proposed IA-based efficient optimisation of per-lane variable speed limits. Yusuf et al. (2025) proposed a Large Language Model-Augmented intelligent conversational agent with a pedagogical purpose. Chen et al. (2025) proposed a CMS-based adaptive edge service distribution solution in efficient communication networks based on wireless technology.

Huang et al. (2025) applied an IA for solving the human depression assessment problem.

Given the increasing number of intelligent systems applied to real-life problem solving, measuring the machine intelligence quotient (MIQ) of IABSs is very important since it should admit their comparison based on intelligence. In previous studies, we showed that the most important property of an intelligence metric must be its universality. Henceforth, developing universal intelligence metrics is difficult due to the large diversity of IABS based on diverse architectures that can be specialized for real-life problem-solving. Previously, we have proved that a feasible approach to ensuring the universality of machine intelligence measurement is to use black-box methods/metrics that can measure the central intelligence tendency, which we call the machine intelligence quotient (MIQ), in difficult problem-solving tasks.

Very few studies worldwide have proposed ways of measuring machine intelligence (Iantovics Gligor et al. 2018). The machine intelligence metrics presented in the scientific literature are based on different philosophies, which makes them difficult to compare effectively. There is no standardisation regarding what constitutes machine intelligence or how to quantify it (Iantovics Gligor et al. 2018).

Previously, we have developed the *MetrIntPairII* (Iantovics, 2021), *MetrIntSimil* (Iantovics et al. 2018), and *ExtrIntDetect* (Iantovics et al. 2019) black-box-based intelligence metrics, which can measure IABSs intelligence, applicable in different situations. In this paper, the focus is on the *MetrIntSimil* metric. *MetrIntSimil* can measure the intelligence of an arbitrary set of IABSs by calculating a so-called intelligence quotient that admits the comparison of IABSs based on their intelligence. The IABSs with statistically the same intelligence are classified in the same classes. In this paper, a difficult-to-decide use case is treated by studying and comparing the intelligence of a set of IABSs. The complexity relies on the specificity of experimental evaluation results that require a complex analysis and difficult decision process, in that seemingly applicable methods give contradictory results.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of state-of-the-art intelligence metrics. In Section 3, we discussed measuring machine intelligence using universal black-box methodologies that we previously proposed. Section 4 presents a challenging use case for measuring the intelligence of a set of studied IABSs using the *MetrIntSimil* metric. This is followed by a discussion section, and finally, the main conclusions are drawn.

BRIEF SURVEY ON STATE-OF-THE-ART MACHINE INTELLIGENCE METRICS

The main purpose of endowing agent-based systems with intelligence is to improve their highly complex problem-solving ability. Human intelligence cannot be fully understood, and there is no consensus vision on a definition of human intelligence. Britannica (www.britannica.com/science/human-intelligence-psychology) provides the following general definition: "Human intelligence is a mental quality consisting of the abilities to learn from experience, adapt to new situations, understand and handle abstract concepts, and manipulate one's environment using knowledge". Brown and Wai (2021) noted that human intelligence is generally correlated with greater success in life. Interestingly, even though human intelligence is impossible to entirely understand, it can be measured by intelligence tests that calculate the so-called intelligence quotient (IQ) (Neisser, 1996). Similarly, the intelligence of IABSs cannot be defined unanimously, but it can be measured. The motivation for the impossibility of giving a unanimously accepted definition to IABSs' intelligence consists in the very large diversity of IABSs with different architectures applicable to solving computing problems.

One of the earliest criteria for measuring machine intelligence was proposed by Alan Turing (1950). A system capable of computation was considered intelligent if a human evaluator could not determine whether the system was artificial or human based on the evaluator's questions, without seeing who was answering.

Newborn (1997) studied the well-known competition between chess grandmaster Garry Kasparov and Deep Blue, an IBM-built chess-playing machine. Schreiner (2000) performed a study on how to measure and compare the intelligence of the systems. Park et al. (2001) proposed the concept of intelligence task graph to measure the intelligence of specific cooperative artificial systems. Sanghi and Dowe (2003) successfully developed a computer program that outperformed the average human intelligence by 100 points on some psychometric tests. Legg and Hutter (2006) developed an intelligence measure based on system performance in difficult-to-evaluate environments. Anthon and Jannett (2007) studied the systems intelligence based on the ability to solve tasks/issues of varying complexity. Hernández-Orallo and Dowe (2010) developed a test that they called the universal anytime intelligence test. Detterman (2011) proposed a challenge to programs by applying human psychometric intelligence tests. Hibbard (2011) developed an intelligence metric based on problem-solving ability in complex environments. Besold et al. (2015) analyzed various problems that are difficult for humans to solve and that could potentially be used as benchmark problems to measure the intelligence of IABSs. Zitnick et al. (2016) proposed measuring machine intelligence based on a specific visual question answering methodology. Sterret (2017) analyzed the competition between Watson, a computer system capable of answering questions formulated in natural language, developed by IBM, and human experts evaluated in the popular game show called Jeopardy. Liu et al. (2017) presented a comprehensive study on the analysis of machine intelligence quotient calculus. Iantovics et al. (2018) proposed the *MetrIntSimil* intelligence metric for measuring

and comparing the intelligence of a set of IABSs and their classification in intelligence classes based on unpaired intelligence measurements. Iantovics et al. (2019) proposed the *ExtrIntDetect* intelligence metric for detecting IABSs with outlier intelligence. Iantovics (2021) proposed the *MetrIntPairII* intelligence metric for measuring and comparing the intelligence of a set of IABSs and their classification in intelligence classes based on paired intelligence measurements. Iantovics (2023) presented a guide for choosing/deciding on the application of specific intelligence metrics. Alidoust (2023) proposed a specific definition of machine intelligence quotient. Long (2024) proposed a novel definition of machine intelligence quotient. Ganuthula and Balaraman (2025) proposed a so-called framework for measuring collaborative human-AI intelligence.

I consider that the measurement of machine intelligence should be based on complex problem-solving abilities. The ultimate goal of measuring machine intelligence is to enable comparison and selection of systems based on their intelligence. Based on the comprehensive study of scientific literature, it would be useful if a metric could classify systems based on their intelligence. Another useful feature would be identifying systems with outlier (statistically significantly different) intelligence from a set of studied IABSs.

The methods for measuring machine intelligence presented in the scientific literature are based on entirely different approaches/methodologies. However, most of these methods cannot be compared directly. One of the main drawbacks of many existing metrics is their limited universality, which makes them impossible to apply to real-life scenarios involving intelligent systems with diverse architectures. Standardizing and making the intelligence metrics universal is an important subject that scientific research must address.

SPECIFICITY OF THE BLACK-BOX METHODS FOR INTELLIGENCE MEASURING

IABSs are defined in diverse ways (Wooldridge and Jennings 1995; Iantovics et al. 2007; Iantovics 2009; Brassai et al. 2012; Iantovics and Zamfirescu 2013; Russell and Norvig 2020). We consider that intelligence must be considered based on the ability to solve difficult problems. Since a difficult problem can be solved by a large diversity of IABSs, an important property of intelligence metrics is the universality. Universality must assure accurate and robust comparisons in intelligence between multiple complex intelligent systems. We have also considered that such a metric must treat the aspect of variability in intelligence and the existence of outlier/extreme intelligence measurements. We understand by outlier intelligence manifestations with statistically very low or high intelligence behavior in specific situations that must be accorded special attention. For instance, a low outlier can appear in a scenario when the response of an IABS is much slower than natural, which could be caused, for instance, by more limited available resources at a certain time, and this aspect is not explicitly known.

In order to assure the universality, we have considered the development of black-box-based metrics as a solution. We proposed in this sense the so-called *MetrIntPairII*, *MetrIntSimil*, and *ExtrIntDetect* metrics.

DIFFICULT-TO-DECIDE USE CASE FOR MEASURING THE INTELLIGENCE OF MORE IABSS

The Universal *MetrintSimil* Intelligence Metric

In a previous work, we have proposed a novel universal black-box based intelligence metric called *MetrintSimil*. *MetrintSimil* is described in detail in (Iantovics et al. 2018). *MetrintSimil* can be applied to an arbitrary set n ($n \geq 2$) of studied IABSSs, denoted in the following as $IntAg = \{IntAg_1, IntAg_2, \dots, IntAg_n\}$, specialized in solving a type of difficult problem. Figure 1 presents a schematic overview of the *MetrintSimil* metric. *MetrintSimil* processing mainly follows the pipeline presented in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Schematic Overview of MetrintSimil Metric

Figure 2: MetrintSimil Metric Processing Pipeline

The calculus, comparison, and classification of MIQs are statistically grounded. The methodology treats aspects of measurement variability and the existence of outlier/extreme intelligence manifestations in different situations.

Experimental Setup

A case study was performed to measure, using the *MetrintSimil* metric, the intelligence of three CMSs, namely intelligent swarm-based systems (composed of very simple agents in that the intelligence emerges at the systems level), denoted in the following $IntAg = \{IntAg_1, IntAg_2, IntAg_3\}$. The CMSs were specialized in solving an NP hard problem, more specifically, the Travelling Salesman problem (TSP) (Kovács et al. 2018). TSP is a classical combinatorial optimization problem that has recently received very large attention, given for its solving (Aguayo et al. 2025; Cohen 2016; Dutta et al. 2025; Lin and Li 2025; Kappagantula et al. 2025; Philip et al. 2025).

Each of the CMS was evaluated on a set of instances of the difficult problem by the same dimensionality, obtaining MQI_1 (experimental problem-solving intelligence evaluation results) for $IntAg_1$; MQI_2 for $IntAg_2$; MQI_3 for $IntAg_3$, with $|MQI_1|=42$ (number of experimental problem-solving intelligence evaluations), $|MQI_2|=44$, $|MQI_3|=39$. Table 1 presents a snapshot of the experimental intelligence evaluation results. Figure 3 shows graphically the evaluation results. Making a visual examination, the values for MQI_1 look slightly higher than those for MQI_2 and MQI_3 . MQI_2 and MQI_3 visually look almost the same.

Table 1: Intelligence Evaluation Results

Exp. eval.	MQI_1	MQI_2	MQI_3
1	7691	5409	6134
2
3	6572	5826	4850
4
.....
39	7447	5101	5926
40	7066	5476	-
41	7277	4405	-
42	6924	5932	-
43	-	5111	-
44	-	5345	-

Figure 3: Graphical Representation of Evaluation Results

Analysis of Experimental Evaluation Data

Table 2 presents the statistical characterization of intelligence evaluation results. StE denotes the standard error. SD denotes the standard deviation. SV ($SV=SD^2$) denotes the variance. IQR denotes the interquartile range. To calculate the IQR, should be found the Q3 (the 75th percentile) and Q1 (the 25th percentile) of a dataset, $IQR = Q3 - Q1$. Q1 and Q3 are found by first ordering the data, followed by finding the median of the lower and upper halves of the data set, respectively. 5%TM denotes the 5% trimmed mean. When using the calculus of the trimmed mean, in most cases, the 5% trimmed mean is chosen, but additional visual representation helps in the decision of the most appropriate value. CIM denotes the confidence interval (CI) of the mean at the 95% confidence level (CL). CL can take different values like, 99%, 90% and 90%. In most of the cases, it is recommended the CI calculus at the 95%CL. Min denotes the minimum. Max denotes the maximum.

The assumption of normality was verified using numerical goodness-of-fit-normality tests. The Shapiro-Wilk (SW) test is known as having more statistical power than the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS), and Lilliefors (Lill) tests (Razali and Wah 2011; Stephens 1974). But the SW test has

disadvantages as well. This includes high sensitivity and the potential for over-rejection of the null hypothesis in large samples. However, it is considered less effective when dealing with outliers or skewed data. Lill test is a modified KS test (it applies a so-called Lilliefors correction). SW test is mostly recommended in case of low sample sizes (≤ 30). Even though the experimental evaluation numbers in the case of all the intelligent systems passed the assumption of 30, it was decided to apply an additional visual validation using the Q-Q plot. Table 3 presents the normality test results using the Lill and SW tests.

Table 2: Intelligence Evaluation Results

Descriptor	MQI_1	MQI_2	MQI_2^*	MQI_3
Mean/ StE	6830.57/ 94.10	5387.71/ 56.85	5410.56/ 53.28	5300.33/ 56.19
CIM	[6640.53, 7020.62]	[5273.06, 5502.35]	[5303.04, 5518.08]	[5186.58, 5414.09]
5%TM	6813.28	5410.61	5432.57	5289.15
Median	6641.5	5434.5	5442	5322
IQR	810	507	444	559
Mode	6612	5579	5579	#N/A
SD	609.85	377.09	349.37	350.93
SV	371920.8	142198.4	122056.25	123151.2
Kurtosis/ StE	-0.16/ 0.72	0.69/ 0.7	0.71/ 0.71	-0.13/ 0.74
Skewness/ StE	0.45/ 0.37	-0.88/ 0.36	-0.78/ 0.36	0.38/ 0.38
Range	2517	1527	1467	1503
Min/Max	5780/ 8297	4405/ 5932	4465/ 5932	4631/ 6134

Min or max value does not necessarily mean statistical outlier. An outlier value influences the mean more significantly than the median. Outlier detection is necessary in many cases, such as the calculation of the mean. The Grubbs (GB) test, also called the extreme studentized deviate method (Barnett and Lewis 1994; Grubbs 1950; Grubbs 1969), can be applied for the statistical outliers (low and high) detection. The assumption for the application of the GB test is the data normality or approximate normality. The GB test applied to a dataset must meet the minimal criteria that include at least 3 data points. At an application, GB can detect a single outlier (the most significant outlier) if it exists. After the removal of the outlier, it can be verified if another outlier still exists. The outlier detection test could be applied consecutively more times until no other outliers are detected. It is recommended the application of the GB test at $\alpha_{GB}=0.05$, two-sided significance level.

The search for outliers was first appreciated based on the box-plot visual inspection (Richard 2009) and followed by the application of the GB test based on the expected normality assumption.

The normality tests are considered at the $\alpha_{norm}=0.05$ significance level. The results in Table 3 show that both MQI_1 and MQI_3 passed the assumption of normality for both Lill and SW tests ($p_{norm}>\alpha_{norm}$). These results are partially confirmed by Figures 4 and 8. Figures 5 and 9 do not indicate the presence of outliers. This is also confirmed by the GB test application on MQI_1 and MQI_3 data, which did not find significant outlier intelligence measurements.

Table 3: Normality Test Results

Int. Syst.	Lilliefors			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	p_{norm}	Statistic	df	p_{norm}
MQI_1	0.136	42	0.052	0.969	42	0.306
MQI_2	0.1	44	0.2	0.935	44	0.016 [#]
MQI_3	0.083	39	0.2	0.987	39	0.625
<i>Reevaluation after elimination of the outlier from MQI_2</i>						
MQI_2^*	0.84	43	0.2	0.95	43	0.57

Passing of the normality assumption failed ($0.016<0.05$).

Figure 4: Q-Q Plot of MQI_1

Figure 5: Box Plot of MQI_1

For MQI_2 , the numerical normality tests Lill and SW gave contradictory results. The Lill test indicates passing the normality assumption, and the SW test indicates the failure to pass the normality assumption. Figure 6 validates the result of the SW test. Figure 7 indicates that the intelligence measurement value 4405 have as influence a small departure but is not a significant outlier. Applying the GB test on MQI_2 data indicated that 4405 is just a value that is furthest from the rest, but is not a significant outlier.

Based on this result, it was decided to remove 4405 from MQI_2 , obtaining $MQI_2^*=MQI_2-\{4405\}$. For MQI_2^* , the descriptive statistical characterization is presented in Table 2 in the column labeled as MQI_2^* . Table 3 presents the results of normality assumption verification. Both normality tests, Lill and SW, applied to MQI_2^* passed the assumption of normality. That was additionally partially validated using Figure 10, which indicates some values with a small departure that is confirmed by Figure 11. Since the normality assumption passed (Lill and SW tests), the decision was not to remove the values with a small departure. The respective

values were not identified by the GB test as statistically significant outliers, just further from the rest.

Figure 6: Q-Q Plot of MQI_2

Figure 7: Box Plot of MQI_2

Figure 8: Q-Q Plot of MQI_3

Figure 9: Box Plot of MQI_3

Figure 10: Q-Q Plot of MQI_2^*

Figure 11: Box Plot of MQI_2^*

Since the data passed the normality assumption, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied to MQI_1 , MQI_2^* , and MQI_3 at the significance level α_{anova} , whose nullhypothesis H_0 failed, $p_{anova}=0.0001$ ($p_{anova}<\alpha_{anova}$). This indicates that the variation among the means is significantly greater than expected by chance. Since the ANOVA test assumes that the data are sampled from populations with identical SDs. This assumption was tested using the Bartlett test at the significance level $\alpha_{bartlett}=0.05$, obtaining Bartlett statistics=17.38 and $p_{bartlett}=0.001$ p-value. $0.001<0.05$ indicates that the difference among SDs is statistically significant, and based on this fact, the application of the ANOVA test is not correct.

The failure of application of the ANOVA test indicates the necessity of application of a transformation (like reciprocal or log) on the data, or alternatively, the application of a non-parametric test. The decision was the application of the Kruskal-Wallis (KW) non-parametric test at the α_{kw} significance level. The p-value denoted p_{kw} of the KW test by $p_{kw}=0.0001$ and KW statistics=81.611 (corrected for ties) indicates that the variation among the medians of MQI_1 , MQI_2^* , and MQI_3 is significantly larger than expected by chance. Table 4 presents the calculation details as a result of the application of the KW test.

Since the nullhypothesis was rejected, Dunn's Multiple comparison test was applied at significance level $\alpha_{dunn}=0.05$, with the results presented in Table 5. The p-value of Dunn's Multiple comparison test is denoted p_{dunn} . The obtained results indicate that MQI_1 significantly differs (it is statistically significantly higher) from both MQI_2^* and MQI_3 . However, the intelligence of $IntAg_1$ is statistically

significantly higher than the intelligence of $IntAg_2$ and $IntAg_3$.

Table 4: KW Test Calculation Details

Int. eval	Number of evaluations	Sum of Ranks	Mean of Ranks
MQI_1	42	4322	102.9
MQI_2^*	43	1985.5	46.174
MQI_3	39	1442.5	36.987

Table 5: Dunn's Multiple Comparison Test Results

Comparison	Mean rank difference	p_{dunn}	Significant difference
MQI_1 vs MQI_2^*	56.73	~ 0.001	YES
MQI_1 vs MQI_3	65.918	< 0.001	YES
MQI_2^* vs MQI_3	9.187	> 0.05	NO

Additionally, MQI_2^* and MQI_3 were statistically compared. Based on the non-normality assumption and non-pairwise evaluations, the Mann-Whitney (MW) non-parametric two-sample test with two tails was applied at the significance level $\alpha_{MW}=0.05$. Obtaining, $p_{MW}=0.0834$, Mann-Whitney U-statistic=651.5, $U'=1025.5$, Sum of rank of $MQI_2=1971.5$, Sum of ranks in $MQI_3=1431.5$. $0.0834 > 0.05$ indicates the acceptance of the null hypothesis. Based on this fact, it can be considered that $IntAg_2$ and $IntAg_3$ have statistically the same intelligence and can be classified in the same intelligence class.

DISCUSSIONS

Universality of Intelligence Metrics

Intelligent systems have a large diversity of applications in diverse domains. It should be noted that although measuring a system's intelligence is important, few methods have been proposed for measuring machine intelligence. A motivation for our research is the difficulty of ensuring universality in the context of an extremely large diversity of IABSs, which can be individual intelligent agents or intelligent cooperative multiagent systems.

In this paper, we considered the measurement of IABS intelligence using a universal black-box-based metric called *MetrintSimil*, presenting a difficult-to-decide use case.

Limitations of the Research

In statistical analyses, an effect size is a quantitative measure of the strength of the relationship between two variables, or the significance of a difference between groups, in a population (Cohen 2016; Kelley and Preacher, 2012).

It was decided on the calculus of the Eta-squared effect size (η^2 , $\eta^2 \in [0,1]$). Higher values signify a greater effect. We consider the interpretation of η^2 as: small effect, $\eta^2 < 0.01$; medium effect, $\eta^2 \in [0.01, 0.06)$; and large effect, $\eta^2 \geq 0.14$. It must be noticed that for a more appropriate interpretation, it is important to conduct additional research and to consider the context and the specificity of the research domain. Applied on the obtained data it was obtained $\eta^2=0.65$, which indicates a large effect size. However, it can be concluded that the magnitude of the detected difference is large. Also,

additionally Cohen's f^2 (Steiger 2004) can be calculated, where $f^2 = \eta^2 / (1 - \eta^2)$.

The effect size in the actual study was calculated after performing the experimental intelligence evaluations. It is recommended in statistical analysis of intelligence indicators results, determining aspects like the test power, sample size, effect size, and the significance level to be performed before collecting the experimental intelligence indicators data, and that these decisions taken based on specific indepth statistical analysis.

Guide for Decision on Appropriate Intelligence Metrics

In this paper it was presented a difficult use case in that was applied the *MetrintSimil* intelligence metric. In the following, we briefly discuss the choosing between *MetrintPairII* (Iantovics 2021), *MetrintSimil* (Iantovics et al. 2018), and *ExtrIntDetect*, that were previously developed (Iantovics et al. 2019).

All these metrics are applicable to measuring the intelligence of a set n ($n \geq 2$) of IABSs. Measuring the intelligence of a single IABS without using the measurement results in comparisons with other IABS does not make any sense.

MetrintPairII and *MetrintSimil* are able to measure the intelligence of the IABSs, with the measurement results being comparable. They can classify the studied IABSs into intelligence classes. An intelligence class can include two or more IABSs with statistically the same intelligence (solve the difficult problems with the same intelligence). Both of them are black-box-based methods. The difference between them consists in the experimental evaluation methodology, which consists of non-pairwise evaluations (*MetrintSimil*) and pairwise evaluations (*MetrintPairII*). Based on this specificity, the mathematical modeling of each of them is different. A limitation of both metrics consists in the fact that they are not able to detect the systems with outlier low and outlier high intelligence (maximal or minimal intelligence does not mean outlier). This limitation is supplemented by the *ExtrIntDetect* metric, which is able to detect the intelligent systems with outlier intelligence (genius IABSs and retarded IABSs). However, based on the specificity of experimental intelligence evaluations (pairwise or non-pairwise), one of the metrics, *MetrintPairII* or *MetrintSimil*, is applicable (decided based on the pairwise criteria). After this, if it is considered, the *ExtrIntDetect* metric can be applied additionally.

CONCLUSIONS

In a previous research, a novel universal black-box-based metric called *MetrintSimil* was introduced for measuring the machine intelligence of a set of studied intelligent systems specialized in solving a highly complex type of problem. The metric can calculate the machine intelligence quotient of each IABS that is comparable and can classify the IABSs with statistically the same intelligence in the same class. *MetrintSimil* can treat the variability in intelligence and the presence of outlier intelligence manifestations. Based on this fact is accurate and robust at the same time.

In this paper, we treated a difficult use case that presents the decisions for the correct application of the *MetrintSimil* metric. This could help intelligent system researchers and

developers to make a correct measurement of their system's intelligence.

The next research will be focused on aspects related to the initial establishment of the experimental design for the application of blackboard-based intelligence metrics for experimental evaluation, which will include treating subjects as controls, the type II error rate (β) by establishing the required number of experimental evaluations of the intelligent systems, additional analysis of statistical power, effect size, and others. These are very important subjects since, in actual artificial intelligence research, the subject of necessary sample size is almost unapproached. Generally speaking, a larger data sample is considered better, but the question is, how large is necessary?

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